

GROWTH OF PUBLIC WORK IN MADRAS STATE DURING 1952 – 1962

Dr. K. Mangayarkarasi

Assistant Professor, Department of History, NGM College, Pollachi,
Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. K. Mangayarkarasi, "Growth of Public Work in Madras State During 1952 – 1962", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 146-147, 2017.

The state of MADRAS had undergone a spectacular development in the administration of Irrigation and Electricity departments during the period of 1952-1962. The state of MADRAS had occupied a prime place in Agriculture and Industry since 1951 in the economic map of INDIA. The cabinet of the MADRAS state which was led by C. Rajaji and K. Kamaraj paid maximum attention to improve the economic status of the population of INDIA.

An amount of Rs.1600 lakhs was spent on TUNGABHADRA and Lower BHAVANI projects. Remission was granted by the government under the Godavari system, Krishna delta system, Cauvery delta system, Pennar delta system and Palar anicut system. The remission for the year under the heads of the productive and non-productive were Rs.7,64,662 and Rs.3,27,082 respectively.

In addition to these developments, 138 works were sanctioned for execution under the control of the Superintending Engineer, Food Production Circle. The area estimated to be benefitted by this scheme was about 3845 acres. An additional quantity of 1733 tons of food grains was produced as a result of the improvement works. The total number of works completed during the period of 1952 – 1962 was 289 at the cost of Rs. 12,53,914. The area benefitted by these works was 12,050, acres resulting in an additional yield of 6457 tons of food grains annually.

Formation of a new tank across the Narallavagu in Sankaravaram village of Udayagiri Taluk, Nellore district was started. An overflow dam was constructed across Thalavarampudi maduvu to divert supplies to the Kattiam pandal tank in Chengalpat district.

Totally 117 other schemes were undertaken in the state to facilitate and to bring more areas under irrigation during this period. The Government of MADRAS followed Grow More Food Schemes which were originally introduced during the Second World War period to improve the food supplies. Several major schemes taken up for execution in the year 1951 were completed in the year 1952.

The permanent achievement of the first cabinet of Independent INDIA paved the way for the construction of Lower Bhavani Project in Coimbatore district. The masonry portion of the dam was completed in 1952. The work was completed in the Earth dam for a length of three miles and in the remaining portions the embankment was formed to a height above the spillway crest line.

Practically all the bridges in the main canal and the extension canal were completed except two or three which were also in advanced stage of progress in 1952. All the distributaries coming in the main canal area were taken up for execution and about 70 percent of the earth work was done. The canal was opened on 14th September 1952 for irrigation in the head reached up to 6 miles and a new area of about 5,000 acres was irrigated during 1952 – 53.

The second achievement of the First Cabinet was the successful completion of Malambuzha project in the Malabar area of the MADRAS state. Under the main masonry dam disposal arrangements in the rear of the right side sluice was completed. The other subsidiary dams were in various stages of progress.

The third irrigation project was the construction work of the METTUR canal of the then MADRAS government. Forty seven out of the forty eight under tunnel works in the right bank canal were completed. All siphons except two and all regulators except one were completed. Work was practically completed in the pressure aqueduct section and the bridge portion. The fourth successful irrigation project was MANIMUTHAR Reservoir Scheme. A GHAT road for two miles in length was also formed. The fifth project was WALAYAR project. The sixth project was Tungabhadra project.

Now coming to the Electricity department. The electricity department was satisfactory during the period of 1952-1962. The Gross revenue was Rs. 517 lakhs. The return capital was 4.8 percent. Due to the failure of the monsoons, 25 percent were cut in the supply of electrical energy to all but essentials services in the hydro-electric areas was imposed at the beginning of MAY 1st, 1952 and 50 percent from MAY 15th, 1952. Inflows in June 1952 however enabled the withdrawal of the cut from 1st July, 1952.

The demand of power for industrial and agricultural purposes was in the increase. In view of the paucity of finance inadequately of generating and transformer capacity and adverse climatic conditions the entire demand was not met. The aggregate of the power demands on the Government systems during the year 1952-1953 was 166,120 kilowatts. And the power generated amounted 795.447 million units. The licensees generated 3.888 million units of power. Thus the total generation in the MADRAS state was to be tonne of 799.335 million units, a decrease of 0.8 percent over the figures for the year 1952.

As usual, top priority was the given in the matter of supply to agricultural loads with a view to aid the Grow More Food Campaign. The work connected with the Five Year plan of Power development in the MADRAS State was in full swing and a total capital expenditure of Rs. 4,69 crores was incurred on major projects and transmission lines. One of the major projects included in the Five Year plan was the Moyar Hydro Electric Scheme commenced its operation in 1953.

During this period the Highways Department also marked a great development. It was the head of the National highways, State highways and District Boards in the Madras State. The total strength of the Engineering establishment of the department was 810 from the ranks of superiors and above.

The Pugalur Bridge Division was closed in 1953. Twelve special subdivisions were formed in t the state. During the year 1952-1953, eighty sections were formed and 22 of them were closed before the end of the year. The length of government and District Board Roads under various categories of roads maintained by the department in 1953 were 15,650 miles and 25,838 miles respectively.

The expenditure on the maintenance of government roads and District board roads in 1953 was Rs.4,51,29,914 and Rs. 4,45,39,379 respectively. Rural development works were undertaken by the State government in 1953.

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